

Support for identifying research directions in fast-growing areas

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Introduction

The number of documents in many research areas is growing rapidly and it is difficult to keep track of what the latest research directions are. There are standardized classification codes in some areas. Two examples are the ACM Computing Classification System and the system for Mathematics Subject Classification. These systems are hierarchical; the top level corresponds to different research areas in Computing and Mathematics respectively, and the lower levels correspond to research directions within these areas. If documents are tagged with such classification codes one can search for documents belonging to different research directions and plot trends that show which directions that are growing/declining etc. However, such standardized classification systems are static and do not easily adapt to new trends and research directions. Therefore, static classification systems are not widely used in fast-growing areas such as Computer Science. In fast-growing areas one needs to dynamically identify research directions based on a corpus of documents in the research area.

One dynamic approach for identifying research directions is to form clusters of author-defined keywords. However, approaches where common keywords are automatically extracted often result in lists of keywords that are either too general to be useful when identifying research directions, e.g., 'model', 'data' and 'application', or confusing when identifying research directions, e.g., 'big data analysis' different from 'data analysis'; 'library' different from 'college library'; and 'big data analytics' different from 'data analytics'.

In a recent study a tool, in the form of a Python program, and a process for identification of research directions in the large research area of Big Data were developed (Lundberg, 2022). The study looked at 118 611 documents from the years 2012 to 2021 from the Scopus database. The main result was a list of the 10 most important research directions in Big Data (e.g., Machine Learning, Internet of Things, and Cloud Computing). These directions were obtained using semi-automatic data mining by providing tool support to research area experts. The main tasks for the experts were to define a blacklist and a thesaurus. The blacklist contained keywords that were too general to be useful when identifying research direction. The thesaurus grouped related keywords into research directions.

Based on the blacklist and thesaurus, the program ranked the research directions considering three criteria: Number of documents in the research direction, number of citations to documents in the research direction, and the growth of the number of documents in the research direction. The program then calculated statistics and generated plots for the most important directions, thus giving a very useful overview of the development and trends in the research area.

We propose, and provide initial evaluation of, ways to automate the task of forming a useful thesaurus. Extending the existing tool with this kind of functionality would significantly reduce the human effort for mining out research directions.

Process Overview

Figure 1 shows the process for mining out directions within a research area. In Step 1 the research area and time period that we are interested in are sent to the program. In Step 2 the program sends queries to Scopus using a Python API. The results from these queries are sent back to the program (Step 3). Based on the information from Scopus, the program identifies the most frequent keywords and some statistics about these keywords. This information is in Step 4 presented to the research area experts that then define a blacklist and thesaurus that are sent to the program in Step 5. The blacklist and thesaurus affect the keywords and statistics, e.g., keywords that are put on the blacklist and keywords that are clustered in a research direction in the thesaurus will disappear from the statistics. However, the research directions that are defined in the thesaurus will appear in the statistics. This means that when Step 4 is repeated the information displayed to the experts will change. Steps 4 and 5 are repeated until the experts are satisfied with the blacklist and thesaurus. The most important research directions are then automatically identified by the program based on the three criteria mentioned in the Introduction. In Step 6 the program generates plots and tables showing trends, citation patterns etc. for the most important research directions.

It is probably not desirable to completely eliminate the human experts in Figure 1. However, large parts of the blacklist can be reused from one research area to another, e.g., keywords such as 'data', 'research' and 'future'. The main effort for the experts is to

define the thesaurus. Here we discuss ways of making this task more automatic and less laborious.

Generating a Thesaurus

In the Python program, a keyword is represented as a set containing the documents for which the keyword is present in either the title, the list of author-defined keywords, or the abstract. A research direction is represented as a cluster of sets; one set for each keyword. We define an optimal thesaurus in the following way:

Consider n non-empty sets A_i ($i = 1 \dots n$). A pair of sets can be disjoint, partly overlapping or one set being a subset of the other. A cluster C_j is a non-empty set containing some of the n sets A_i . No set A_i can belong to more than one cluster. We refer to a partition of sets into k clusters as a k -clustering. The sets in a k -clustering are renumbered so that sets 1 to n_1 belong to C_1 , sets n_1+1 to n_2 belong to C_2, \dots , sets $n_{k-1}+1$ to n_k belong to C_k and sets n_k+1 to n do not belong to any cluster. Consider a k -clustering such that $\left| \bigcup_{i=n_{j-1}+1}^{n_j} A_i \right| \geq m, j = 1 \dots k$ (we define $n_0 = 0$). We refer to this as a *valid k -clustering*. Consider a set A_x such that $A_x \in C_y$ for some cluster C_y . The *coherence* for A_x is defined as $C(A_x) = \frac{|A_x \cap (\bigcup_{i=n_{y-1}+1}^{x-1} A_i) \cup (\bigcup_{i=x+1}^{n_y} A_i)|}{|A_x \cap (\bigcup_{i=1}^{n_{y-1}} A_i) \cup (\bigcup_{i=n_y+1}^n A_i)| + 1}$ (we define $\bigcup_{i=1}^{n_{y-1}} A_i = \emptyset$). The average coherence for a valid k -clustering is $\sum_{i=1}^{n_k} C(A_i) / n_k$. A valid k -clustering with maximum (high) average coherence corresponds to an optimal (good) thesaurus.

In the study concerning the research area Big Data, m was set to 2500 documents and k was set to 17 research directions by the research area experts.

Discussion

The concepts valid k -clustering and average coherence was implemented in a computer program. Our evaluation consisted of two experiments. In Experiment 1 we compared the coherence of an expert defined thesaurus with the coherence of 500 randomly modified thesauruses. The experiment showed that the coherence metric reflects the experts' opinions, making it possible to automatically calculate good thesauruses. However, more research is needed before the task of defining a thesaurus can be completely automated.

In Experiment 2 we looked at the 100 most frequent keywords that were not allocated to a research direction. For 82 keywords it was not possible to find a research direction so that the average coherence increased (which was not surprising since the experts already looked at the keywords), but for 18 keywords it was possible to find a research direction so that the average coherence increased. These recommendations were shown to the experts and for 15 out of these 18 keywords the experts strongly agreed with the recommendation.

This experiment indicated that it is already now possible to automatically add keywords to research directions based on an initial thesaurus generated by experts. In fact, Experiment 2 indicated that the quality of the thesaurus could be improved by using automatic calculations of coherence and valid k -clustering. Without the support of a computer program the experts can easily overlook some keywords when the thesaurus is defined.

References

- Lundberg, L. (2022). Bibliometric Mining of Research Directions and Trends for Big Data, Retrieved November 12, 2022 from: <https://www.researchsquare.com/article/rs-2233095/v1>.

Figure 1. The process and program for mining out research directions within a research area.